

Misfolded Fate: Amyloidosis, the Gut-Microbiome, and Neurodegeneration

KEY WORDS

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ABSTRACT

Neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD) are a growing global health burden that is only getting worse as the population continues to age. Despite their clinical differences, these disorders share a core pathological feature: the misfolding and aggregation of proteins into β -sheet-rich amyloid structures that resist degradation and propagate in a prion-like manner. Increasing evidence suggests that oligomers disrupt ion homeostasis and neuronal membrane activity, indicating that oligomers represent the most toxic form of amyloid proteins rather than mature fibrils. The brain-centered view of neurodegeneration has been expanded to include the gut microbiome. Gut microbes and their products may contribute to the initiation and propagation of neurodegeneration and cognitive decline. This review examines the key components of amyloid biochemistry, including structure and mechanisms of formation and toxicity. It also examines the role of microbiome-driven contributions and potential therapeutic targets.

INTRODUCTION

Neurodegenerative disorders (NDDs) represent a major global health crisis and are characterized by progressive neuronal loss that leads to irreversible cognitive, behavioral, and/or motor decline. Most well-known and most prevalent, Alzheimer's Disease

(AD) affects 7.2 million individuals in the United States alone (Alzheimer's Association, 2025). The economic burden exceeds \$400 billion annually in unpaid caregiving alone (Alzheimer's Association, 2025). Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common age-related NDD and affects approximately 1 million Americans (Willis et al., 2022). Although less common, PD still imposes a considerable economic burden, nearly \$61.5 billion annually (Parkinson's Foundation, 2025). NDDs reduce the quality of life of patients while also placing immense strain on health care systems and families. They will only become more prevalent as the population continues to age and live longer, making it increasingly important to determine the mechanisms underlying these diseases and developing treatments.

Many NDDs share similar molecular dysfunctions, even though signs and symptoms vary depending on the brain regions affected. A unifying feature across NDDs is the misfolding and aggregation of specific proteins into amyloid structures in and around cells. Amyloids aggregate in many different tissues throughout the body, but when they accumulate in the brain, they have devastating sensory, motor, and cognitive effects. In AD, the proteins amyloid- β (A β) and tau aggregate at various levels ultimately resulting in amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles, whereas in PD, the protein α -synuclein (α -syn) aggregates into Lewy bodies (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012; Erkinen et al., 2018). These three proteins share the ability to misfold and assemble into fibrils that may self-propagate in a prion-like manner (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012; Erkinen et al., 2018). In classical prion diseases, a normally folded protein becomes pathogenic when misfolded and can recruit other copies of the normally folded protein to adopt the abnormal conformation (Goedert et al., 2010; Hall & Masood, 2025). Similarly, in AD and PD, misfolded protein aggregates can encourage the misfolding of normally folded proteins and spread between neighboring cells resulting in cell-to-cell propagation of

pathology (Goedert et al., 2010). The capacity for long distance propagation suggests that neurodegenerative pathology is not isolated to the brain but instead involves multiple interconnected systems. The gut microbiome has emerged as a key player in the initiation and progression of AD and PD.

AMYLOID PROTEINS: STRUCTURE, FORMATION, AND BIOLOGY

Within the human body, there are tens of thousands of proteins, each with its own specific structure and function (Rehman et al., 2022). They are the most structurally complicated biological macromolecule and move through three to four different levels of folding (Rehman et al., 2022). The primary structure is a linear chain of amino acids, the building blocks of proteins (Rehman et al., 2022). The secondary structure is formed via hydrogen bonding of the protein's backbone (Rehman et al., 2022). There are two major secondary structures: alpha helices (tight coils stabilized by internal hydrogen bonds) and beta-pleated sheets, where two different regions of the protein lie side by side and are held together by "external" hydrogen bonds (Rehman et al., 2022). The tertiary and sometimes quaternary structures of a protein are three-dimensional shapes driven by side chain interactions (Rehman et al., 2022). Changes to protein structure can cause a wide variety of diseases (Rehman et al., 2022). Notably, prion diseases and diseases involving amyloid proteins result from changes to the secondary structure of various proteins (Rehman et al., 2022).

From a pathological perspective, amyloids are unbranched fibers that typically aggregate extracellularly (though this is not always the case, for example, tau aggregates intracellularly), are found *in vivo*, and bind Congo Red and exhibit green birefringence when viewed between crossed polarizers (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Green birefringence is an optical phenomenon in which the Congo Red bound to amyloids refract polarized light and emit

a green signal (Howie, 2019). Based on the pathological definition, fewer than 25 amyloids are associated with serious disease (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Biophysicists, in contrast, define amyloids as exhibiting a cross- β fiber diffraction pattern (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). A cross- β diffraction pattern occurs when the β -pleated sheets of the protein run perpendicular to the fibril axis, producing two signals that form a cross when viewed using X-ray diffraction (Greenwald & Riek, 2010). This structure is found in amyloids formed by completely unrelated proteins (proteins with no amino acid sequence similarity), indicating that amyloid formation reflects an energetically favorable conformational state under certain conditions rather than a result of specific sequences (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012).

Amyloid structures are composed of β -sheets arranged in highly stable parallel or antiparallel orientations and resist degradation or clearing by the body's natural waste-removal mechanisms (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Side chains in the β -sheet amino acids interlock, creating highly stable steric zippers (like the zipper of a jacket) with internal hydrophobic regions (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). The stability and resilience of amyloid protein structures contribute to their long-term persistence in neural tissue, allowing aggregates to accumulate over extended periods and ultimately reach a threshold that disrupts cellular function, leading to symptom onset.

Amyloid formation proceeds through sequential stages: monomer, oligomer, protofibril, fibril, and plaque formations (Figure 1, Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Proteins enter the amyloid state when their backbone amide (N-H and C=O) groups become exposed to other proteins (related OR unrelated), allowing the formation of hydrogen bonds between the two (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). This transformation can be triggered by denaturation, protein overexpression, cleavage into fragments, or overproduction of natively disordered proteins (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). The

resulting amyloid intermediates expose their hydrophobic regions, leading to a high affinity for aggregation and the formation of insoluble plaques (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012).

FIGURE 1

Illustration of the amyloid formation pathway, showing the progression from soluble monomers to oligomers, elongated protofibrils, insoluble mature fibrils, and finally large plaques.

Proteins in the amyloid state can act as seeds that induce misfolding in properly folded proteins, thus propagating the amyloid structure (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). This process resembles the behavior of infectious prions, giving amyloid-related NDDs the term “prion-like.” Amyloids can also induce misfolding and aggregation of different proteins, a phenomenon known as cross-seeding (Curto et al., 2022). Cross-seeding may explain comorbidities and accelerated disease progression in the presence of multiple amyloid species. Many studies have shown that >50% of AD patients exhibit significant Lewy body pathology (accumulation of α -syn and ubiquitin into intracellular inclusions) (Bassil et al., 2021). Others report A β plaques in PD patients (Bassil et al., 2021). Combined pathology is frequently observed, and patients with the combination often experience worse symptomology and shortened life expectancies (Bassil et al., 2021).

Amyloids are heavily associated with disease, but not all are toxic. Functional amyloids are involved in a wide range of biological processes, including hormone storage, melanin formation, biofilm production, and the launch of antiviral innate immune response (Curto et al., 2022; Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012; Friedland & Chapman, 2017). Structurally, they are no different from pathological amyloids, indicating that amyloid proteins do not inherently cause disease. Instead, disease occurs when regulatory

mechanisms fail or become overwhelmed. Further research on the structure, formation, and mechanisms of amyloid proteins is needed, but proves difficult. A challenge in amyloid studies is that *in vitro* models may not accurately reflect how specific proteins would behave *in vivo*; however, these studies provide insight into the underlying biophysical principles of amyloids and establish a framework for *in vivo* interpretation (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012).

AMYLOIDS IN MAJOR NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASES

NDDs are characterized by the accumulation of misfolded proteins in the central nervous system (CNS), proteostasis collapse, and chaperone overload (Bose & Cho, 2017). Proteostasis is the biological process of ensuring the proper synthesis, folding, and degradation of proteins (Shukla & Narayan, 2025). Neurons are especially vulnerable to proteostasis failure because they do not undergo cell division, which prevents abnormal protein dilution and increases chances for abnormal aggregation (Bose & Cho, 2017). However, each NDD varies based on the amyloid protein, brain region, and affected neuronal processes.

Prion Diseases

Prion diseases are caused by the misfolding of normal human prion protein (PrP^C) into the pathogenic version (PrP^{Sc}), an infectious amyloid that self-propagates (Hall & Masood, 2025). PrP^C mostly contains alpha helices, whereas PrP^{Sc} contains the characteristic β -sheet composition (Hall & Masood, 2025). Prion diseases are classified as sporadic, inherited, or acquired, with sporadic being the most common (e.g., Sporadic Creutzfeldt-Jakob Disease) (Hall & Masood, 2025). The cerebral cortex, basal ganglia, cerebellum, and thalamus may all be affected depending on the specific prion disease (Nafe et al., 2023). Prion diseases are characterized by rapid and severe cognitive decline and motor dysfunction, and are ultimately fatal, with death occurring within one year of onset in

70% of patients (Hall & Masood, 2025). Prion disease research provides a conceptual framework that aids in understanding the spread of amyloid pathologies in AD and PD, especially when it comes to seeding.

Alzheimer's Disease (AD)

AD is pathologically defined by two main protein aggregates: extracellular A β plaques and intracellular tau tangles (Erkkinen et al., 2018). A β is formed from the cleavage of amyloid precursor protein (APP) by β -secretase and γ -secretase (Chen et al., 2017). The gene that encodes APP is found on chromosome 21, explaining why individuals with Down Syndrome (trisomy 21) have an increased risk of developing AD due to inherently increased concentration of misfolded versions (Rubenstein et al., 2024). AD is primarily an amnesic disorder that affects semantic memory (the recall of general knowledge and facts) and episodic memory (the ability to remember personal experiences and events) both of which are processed in the medial part of the temporal lobe and the hippocampus, but it often progresses to include motor dysfunction in late stages (Erkkinen et al., 2018; Mujuwar et al., 2021). Changes associated with AD are thought to begin 20 years before symptomology is reported, making early diagnosis a worthwhile pursuit (Villemagne et al., 2013). Currently, scientists can identify abnormal levels of A β and tau in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and just recently, in 2025, the FDA approved the blood test that detects abnormal levels of A β and tau, making testing more readily available to patients (Alzheimer's Association, 2025; U.S. Food & Drug Administration, 2025). Positron emission tomography (PET) imaging is also used to visualize accumulations for research and diagnostic purposes (Alzheimer's Association, 2025). PET scans are performed by injecting a radioactive tracer into the bloodstream, which travels to the brain and binds to amyloid deposits (Chapleu et al., 2022). A PET scan is considered positive

when there is significant amyloid plaque formation, indicated by increased tracer uptake in the gray matter (Chapleu et al., 2022). PET scans can also be used to assess glucose metabolism, providing an estimate of neuronal energy usage and synaptic function (Alhasan et al., 2025).

Parkinson's Disease (PD)

Parkinson's disease is characterized by the accumulation of α -syn and ubiquitin into intracellular inclusions called Lewy bodies (Erkkinen et al., 2018). Most commonly, Lewy bodies are found in the substantia nigra, a key structure of the midbrain responsible for fine motor control but may also appear in peripheral structures such as the gastrointestinal (GI) tract (Huh et al., 2023). PD pathology also involves the degradation of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra (Huh et al., 2023). PD is best known as a movement disorder with symptoms including tremor, bradykinesia, stiffness, and postural instability (Huh et al., 2023). However, PD patients also experience non-motor symptoms, such as olfactory, gastrointestinal, cardiovascular, and urological problems (Friedland & Chapman, 2017). Notably, gastrointestinal symptoms such as constipation often precede motor symptoms by many years, suggesting that α -syn pathology may originate in the gut (Friedland & Chapman, 2017).

MECHANISMS OF AMYLOID TOXICITY

Although amyloid aggregation is often discussed in terms of large plaques or fibrils, it remains unclear precisely which form of amyloid aggregation is toxic (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Emerging evidence suggests that oligomers (Figure 1), which are intermediate, soluble aggregates, may be more toxic than mature fibrils and plaques (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). In AD, higher levels of A β oligomers correlate with increased disease severity (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Compared to mature fibrils, oligomers are small

and easily diffusible, allowing them to readily move through the brain (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). The formation of plaques may function as a cellular defense mechanism, protecting cells from the greater toxicity of the smaller, more mobile oligomers by sequestering them (Polymenidou & Cleveland, 2011).

The most accepted theory for amyloid toxicity involves the interaction between oligomers and cellular membrane receptors, leading to disrupted signaling (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Since they are small and diffusible, some researchers believe oligomers may insert themselves into the neuron cell membrane and form a pore-like structure that functions as an unregulated ion channel (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Unregulated channels disrupt membrane integrity and ion homeostasis (particularly calcium) (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Calcium is critical for neuron function, and dysregulation can ultimately trigger cell death, which is critical because once neurons are lost, they are unlikely to be replaced (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012).

THE ROLE OF THE GUT MICROBIOME IN NEURODEGENERATION

The gut microbiome contains trillions of microorganisms that live together in a dynamic community (Curto et al., 2022; Park & Gao, 2024). The microbiome is predominantly composed of bacteria but also includes viruses and fungi (Curto et al., 2022; Park & Gao, 2024). Gut microbes engage in continuous, bidirectional communication with the nervous system and, under normal conditions, contribute to the maintenance of homeostasis (Curto et al., 2022; Park & Gao, 2024). However, alterations in microbial composition, termed dysbiosis, have been linked to various disorders, including neurodegeneration (Curto et al., 2022; Park & Gao, 2024).

Communication Between the Gut and the Brain

The gut and brain communicate in multiple overlapping routes,

allowing intestinal microbes to influence the CNS. Communication between the gut and the brain primarily occurs through signaling from the enteric nervous system (ENS) to the CNS via the vagus nerve (Lu et al., 2024). The ENS is comprised of neurons (cells that transmit electrical impulses) and glial cells (support and maintenance cells) that reside in the intestinal submucosa and muscularis propria (a thick layer of smooth muscle) (Lu et al., 2024). The ENS regulates the GI tract almost independently of the CNS, yet the two remain in constant communication (Lu et al., 2024). The ENS helps maintain an environment that supports gut microbes, which in turn contribute to the development of structural and functional integrity of the ENS through metabolite production (Lu et al., 2024). Some of these metabolites, such as short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), are released into the ENS then travel to the CNS via the vagus nerve, completely bypassing peripheral circulation (Lu et al., 2024). Gut microbes also produce some neurotransmitters, such as serotonin, which is commonly known as a mood regulator but also plays a role in memory, among other functions in the brain and throughout the body (Bamalan et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2024).

Other major pathways influenced by gut-brain communication include immune, endocrine, and metabolite signaling. The gut microbiota plays a role in regulating the maturation and activation of immune cells, including macrophages and T cells (Lu et al., 2024). Macrophages and T cells produce cytokines that can cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB), leading to neuroinflammation, which can be very dangerous if unregulated (Lu et al., 2024). Chronic inflammation can prime microglia, eventually promoting the deposition of amyloids in the brain (Lu et al., 2024). Changes in gut microbiome composition can trigger the release of stress hormones, affecting various physiological processes (Lu et al., 2024). Some microbial metabolites cross the BBB and influence neuronal health for better or for worse (Lu et al., 2024).

There is a growing body of evidence that suggests that amyloid

formation may begin in the gut and then travel to the brain via the ENS (Friedland & Chapman, 2017). Constipation is an early symptom of PD patients, and α -syn deposits have been found in gut neurons (Friedland & Chapman, 2017). In addition, prion diseases, such as bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE or Mad Cow Disease), are transmitted when the host consumes infected food and the prion travels from gut to brain (Friedland & Chapman, 2017). It is not unreasonable to consider that amyloid proteins associated with age-related NDDs may follow a similar pathway, especially considering how similarly they behave to prions.

The Role of Microbial Metabolites in Neurodegeneration

One of the most direct ways in which gut microorganisms influence CNS function is through the production of bioactive metabolites (Park & Gao, 2024). Metabolites act as signaling molecules between gut microbes and the nervous system and can exert effects on immune regulation, BBB integrity, and neuronal health (Park & Gao, 2024). SCFAs have emerged as particularly important modulators of neuroinflammation and amyloid pathology (Park & Gao, 2024).

SCFAs are produced by gut bacteria through the fermentation of dietary fibers. Under normal conditions, SCFAs help maintain the integrity of the BBB, regulate neuroinflammation and neurochemical homeostasis (Lu et al., 2024; Park & Gao, 2024). As people age, the composition of their microbiome becomes less diverse, leading to abnormal bacterial metabolism (Lu et al., 2024; Park & Gao, 2024). Many PD patients have increased intestinal permeability, resulting in excessive SCFAs in the brain and peripheral circulation (Huh et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2024). Abnormal distribution of SCFAs can lead to cognitive decline by modulating microglial activity to favor amyloid deposition (Lu et al., 2024). In one study, dysbiosis in aging mice was shown to stimulate the cleavage of $A\beta$ and tau protein (Lu et al., 2024). Abnormal SCFAs levels

also weaken the integrity of the BBB, allowing cells and substances to cross inappropriately (Lu et al., 2024). One of the important roles of the BBB is regulating immune response signals that can cause inflammation (Friedland & Chapman, 2017). An increase in neuroinflammation is a key factor in cognitive decline in patients with NDDs, rather than the accumulation of amyloid plaques alone (Friedland & Chapman, 2017). Patients with cerebral amyloid deposits were reported to have no cognitive decline, indicating that amyloid deposits alone may be insufficient to cause cognitive impairment and that an accompanying inflammatory response, potentially exacerbated by dysbiosis, is required for the development of cognitive dysfunction (Friedland & Chapman, 2017).

Microbial Amyloid and Cross-Seeding

Many bacteria produce amyloid proteins as part of their normal biology (Curli and FapC are two examples), which may directly contribute to amyloid pathology in NDDs (Curto et al., 2022). Microbial amyloids also share the same structural characteristics (β -sheets, steric zippers, high resistance to degradation) as mammalian pathological amyloids and can induce protein misfolding via cross-seeding mechanisms (Curto et al., 2022). This idea is supported by the prion-like propagation that has already been observed in NDDs.

One of the most understood examples of microbial amyloids is curli proteins, a class of amyloids produced by *Escherichia coli* and related species (Friedland & Chapman, 2017). Curli fibers are produced extracellularly (like most microbial amyloids) and aid in bacterial adhesion, biofilm formation, and host colonization (Friedland & Chapman, 2017). These functional amyloids are highly regulated and lend support to the idea that amyloids are not inherently pathogenic and only cause disease when regulatory measures fail (Friedland & Chapman, 2017).

Because the amyloid structure is more dependent on backbone

interactions rather than specific protein sequences, microbial amyloids can act as seeds for the conversion of human proteins to the amyloid state (Curto et al., 2022). Some evidence suggests that proteins with at least 70% of the same sequence have an easier time cross-seeding each other, whereas other evidence suggests that misfolding is induced more efficiently in proteins with highly unrelated sequences (Curto et al., 2022). Proteome sequencing of gut bacteria revealed that at least 0.3% of all known bacterial genes encode prion-like domains, increasing the potential for amyloid fibril formation that can cross-seed human proteins (Curto et al., 2022). This percentage could be even higher, up to 18%, in pathogenic bacteria (Curto et al., 2022). The widespread presence of prion-like domains and microbial amyloids exposes the host to amyloidogenic material, which under healthy conditions may be benign, but becomes pathogenic as people age, and its concentration begins to overwhelm regulatory mechanisms, coinciding with increased inflammatory processes.

Multiple studies have been conducted where mouse models that received microbiomes from NDD patients demonstrated greater symptomology compared to mice that received microbiomes from healthy patients (Curto et al., 2022). The observations made in these studies may be due to two main issues: the exposure to microbial amyloids that induced misfolding of native proteins in the mice, and abnormal microbiome compositions that contributed to neuroinflammation and cognitive and/or motor decline. The ability of microbial amyloids to seed and induce misfolding of native proteins supports the prion-like propagation model and the idea that the formation of amyloids associated with NDDs may start in the gut.

THERAPEUTIC IMPLICATIONS

The shared pathological mechanism of protein misfolding across NDDs highlights several unified pathways for therapeutic

intervention. Despite differences in clinical presentation, the core challenge remains the same: misfolded proteins enter amyloid states that resist degradation and accumulate into neurotoxic species (Bose & Cho, 2017). Accumulation of amyloid proteins overwhelms cellular quality-control systems and contribute to progressive neuronal decline (Bose & Cho, 2017). A critical obstacle for treatment is the BBB, which significantly restricts the delivery of therapeutic agents to affected brain regions (Curto et al., 2022). As a result, current research is focused on strategies that either prevent amyloid formation, neutralize toxic intermediates, or restore cellular proteostasis (Bose & Cho, 2017; Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Growing recognition of the role of the microbiome also presents novel therapeutic interventions worth exploring (Curto et al., 2022).

One promising direction involves stabilizing proteins in their native conformations, thereby reducing the likelihood of misfolding (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Small molecules, such as 2002-H20, have also been found to bind and disrupt the formation of amyloid intermediates, possibly by accelerating their aggregation into plaques, which are less cytotoxic. (Chen et al., 2011; Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Parallel to this approach are efforts to prevent oligomer and fibril formation (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012). Some peptides, such as the A β segment containing the amino acid sequence KLVFF, are capable of “capping” fibrils to prevent further growth (Eisenberg & Jucker, 2012).

Another strategy focuses on restoring proteostasis, which is severely disrupted in NDDs. Excess misfolded proteins overwhelm chaperones and activate the Unfolded Protein Response (UPR) (Bose & Cho, 2017). Therapeutic efforts aim to modulate chaperone activity or regulate UPR signaling to restore protein-folding homeostasis (Bose & Cho, 2017). Molecular chaperones such as Hsp40, Hsp70, and Hsp90 are of particular interest because they selectively recognize hydrophobic surfaces exposed on non-native

proteins, facilitating proper folding or refolding (Bose & Cho, 2017). Chemical chaperones have also shown efficacy in reducing amyloid load and enhancing autophagy in model systems, but molecular chaperones remain more clinically promising due to their specificity and lower toxicity (Bose & Cho, 2017).

The gut microbiome is an attractive therapeutic target because it is highly responsive to external influences and does not require the crossing of the BBB (Park & Gao, 2024). Examples of therapeutic strategies include dietary modulation, probiotics, prebiotics, and antibiotics. Dietary interventions, such as adhering to a Mediterranean diet, have been associated with reduced inflammation and improved cognitive function (Park & Gao, 2024). Many spices have also been shown to have positive effects on the prevention of NDDs (Park & Gao, 2024). Curcumin (found in turmeric) can help reduce inflammation (Park & Gao, 2024). One study explored the effect of 6-Shogaol (the active ingredient in ginger) on *Proteus mirabilis*-induced PD in mice. Researchers treated mouse models with *P. mirabilis*, a bacterium commonly thought of as a uropathogen but also found in the GI tract, for five days, causing them to develop PD-like motor dysfunction (Huh et al., 2023). The mice that were then treated with either ginger extract or 6-shogaol showed improvement in motor dysfunction and dopaminergic neuron degradation (Huh et al., 2023). In addition to dietary changes, probiotics and prebiotics are other popular methods of modulating the gut microbiome and may present a promising preventative treatment, but more research is needed (Curto et al., 2022). Antibiotics are also capable of modulating the gut microbiome, but they also present severe risks, such as microbiome disruption and antibiotic resistance (Curto et al., 2022).

Targeting the microbiome lends itself to preventive and early intervention frameworks, which are ideal for diseases with long prodromal phases like AD and PD. Combining microbiome alteration approaches with amyloid-targeting therapies may provide a

more comprehensive and effective treatment option.

CHALLENGES

Despite advances in understanding amyloid biology, the gut-brain connection, and their role in neurodegeneration, several challenges and unresolved questions remain. One major limitation is the models that are used to conduct amyloid studies. *In vitro* models have played a significant role in developing the understanding of amyloid formation and interactions but do not accurately model how amyloid proteins may behave in the body. Animal models also present challenges, particularly because they lack the complexity of the human microbiome, immune system, and nervous system. Another issue involves the compounding effect that the microbiome and the CNS have on each other. Because of their bidirectional relationship, forming conclusions about the origin of NDDs is extremely difficult. The long-term nature of NDDs also presents a challenge, as most studies only occur over short periods of time.

Future research should adopt a systems-level approach since it is becoming increasingly clear that NDDs are not strictly isolated to the CNS. Long-term human studies will also prove beneficial in determining whether microbiome changes are the cause or the result of amyloid pathologies. Researchers must also prioritize developing a more comprehensive understanding of amyloid formation and toxicity mechanisms, including the role of microbial amyloid cross-seeding. The development of early biomarker tests may aid in the early detection of AD and PD, facilitating longitudinal tracking and early intervention therapies.

Overall, future research must prioritize the development of therapeutics capable of crossing the BBB and the characterization of the diverse structural forms of amyloids, especially toxic oligomers, which remain poorly defined. Understanding cross-seeding

mechanisms, which may explain overlapping pathologies and comorbid presentations, and identifying early biomarkers that detect oligomer accumulation before irreversible neuronal loss occurs are also crucial areas for research.

CONCLUSION

Amyloid aggregation is a fundamental, unifying pathology underlying major NDDs, including AD, PD, and prion diseases. The spread of misfolded proteins in a “prion-like” manner is a key mechanism of disease progression. Crucially, toxicity is increasingly linked to intermediate oligomers, which may exert harm by forming ion channels in neuronal membranes, leading to calcium dysregulation. Conversely, large aggregates may serve a protective function. An increased understanding of the gut-brain axis has shifted the way neurodegeneration is conceptualized, incorporating the influence of the peripheral systems. Through various communication routes, the gut microbiome may influence amyloid formation and disease progression. Future therapeutic research must overcome the challenge posed by the BBB to effectively deliver agents that target the toxic oligomeric species and restore proteostasis by addressing chaperone overload. Clarifying the highly diverse structures of amyloids and their functional equivalents remains essential to advancing novel and specific treatments.

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